

Analysis of Web Accessible Networks, Organizations and Groups

Task	<u>Analysis of Web Accessible Networks, Organizations and Groups</u>	
Context	The EC project TransSOL (WP 2). Coordinators of this activity were: Maria Kousis (Dept. of Sociology and Center for Research & Studies in Humanities, Social Sciences & Pedagogics, University of Crete) and Yannis Tzitzikas (FORTH-ICS) This task was funded by the University of Crete.	
Description	Identification and analysis of networks, organizations and groups that deal with solidarity in times of crisis, such as citizens' initiatives and networks of cooperation amongst civil society actors, with a strong focus on the fields of unemployment, migration, disabilities.	
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Version History

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0.1	Jan 14, 2016	FORTH	First summary of the results
0.2	Jan 15, 2016	FORTH	More results from 3 Swiss hubs
0.3	Jan 19, 2016	FORTH	Updated results for Polish hubs
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2.0	Mar 3, 2016	FORTH	Added results from all hubs
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2.2	Mar 9, 2016	FORTH	Detailed description of the process (Section 2)
2.3	Mar 16, 2016	FORTH	Updated results for UK
2.4	Mar 23, 2016	FORTH	Added the results of the sampling process
2.5	Apr 21, 2016	FORTH	Inclusion of more transnational organizations

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1 The Purpose

TransSOL¹ is an H2020 EU Project (initiated on June 2015) dedicated to providing systematic and practice-related knowledge about European solidarity at times of crisis. It brings together researchers and civil society practitioners from eight European countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Poland, Switzerland and the United Kingdom). The project has the following main objectives:

1. **Gather systematic data on contextual factors.** The crisis has changed the socio-economic, political and legal context of European solidarity, with different effects in various countries. TransSOL will identify measure and compare the inhibiting or beneficial impact of contextual factors upon European solidarity in different countries.
2. **Assemble a systematic and cross-national database on solidarity in Europe.** European solidarity at times of crisis is manifold in its forms and means. TransSOL will map the broad range of existing practices and projects at the local, national and cross-national levels in order to present a detailed picture of solidarity initiatives and action cases across Europe.
3. **Develop a multidimensional data set that allows measurement and analysis of European solidarity at various levels.** TransSOL will gather and analyze data about attitudes and practices of solidarity at the levels of individual citizens, organizations and inter-organizational fields, and the mass media and the public sphere. This composite data set will allow for a better understanding of solidarity's internal rationale, its conditioning factors and inherent dynamics, and, in particular, the effect of the crisis at all of these levels of solidarity.
4. **Identify best practices for European solidarity and develop evidence-based policy recommendations.** TransSOL seeks to evaluate innovative measures and projects from practitioners' and scientists' points of view, and to improve existing practices. We will also place attention on potential policy solutions and suggest elements of a national and European legal framework which may be conducive to solidarity.

The Work package 2 of TransSOL project, will produce a comparative data set and report about innovative forms of transnational solidarity in times of crisis. This work package is devoted in motoring, analyzing and assessing innovative practices of solidarity in response to crisis, such as citizens' initiatives and networks of cooperation amongst civil society actors, with a strong focus on the fields of unemployment, migration, disabilities.

Dr. Maria Kousis, which is the scientific responsible for University of Crete (UOC) (which participates in the project's consortium), and leader of the work package 2, communicated FORTH discussing the above requirements. Both sides agreed that FORTH could undertake these activities starting from February 1, 2016 and ending on February 29, 2016, and delivering the results after the end of that period. Furthermore the scientific responsible of UOC had the role of being a communication hub between the FORTH team and the TransSOL consortium.

To this end, FORTH, defined the process for analyzing these contents by exploiting publicly available software, or developing new applications whenever required. In this deliverable we

¹ <http://transsol.eu/>

report the process that was followed for analyzing the networks of the eight counties and report the results of this analysis.

2 The Process

The entire process can be divided in four sequential processes. The first one is the extraction of the information from the identified hubs and sub/hubs, as well as from the individual websites. The second step contains the cleaning of the extracted information that are given as input in the third step, which merges all the lists. Finally the lists are exploited for performing the sampling process. Below we describe them in more detail.

Figure 1. The main sequential steps of the entire process

2.1 Extraction

The entry point for the analysis process is a publicly accessible network. In other terms it is a website containing links to other sites. The purpose is to analyze the contents of the network and export them in a form suitable for further analysis (by humans). Since there is not a common format for these networks, each one of them requires a different approach for analyzing it; in some cases the list of sites in a network are inside a table, in other cases there are drop down lists that reveal information for these sites, etc. This practically means that we should handle each network in a different way. In the next section (§ 2.4) we describe the tools and methods that we have used for extracting the contents from the hubs/ sub hubs. We should also note that many of these websites where actually hubs containing information for other hubs.

For each website we used a minimum set of fields to be extracted; these fields are:

- **Title** of the organization
- **URL(-s)** of the website of the organization
- **Contact information** that usually contain the address, the city and region, phone and fax numbers as well as the ZIP code.
- Short **description** of the organization
- **e-mail** address(-es)
- **ZIP** code
- **Date**; it could be creation date, last update date, active since date, etc.

Apart from the minimum set of fields in certain cases the hubs/subhubs contained also more information that were easy to be extracted so we included them in the final lists. Just indicatively such information were region, territory, issue (for some organizations regarding disability issues), etc. Finally as regards the provided individual websites we extracted all the aforementioned information from them manually. Figure 2 shows an indicative screenshot from a Polish hub about disability that shows the information that have been extracted. More specifically the red rectangles show the information as they can be found on the website of the hub.

Figure 2. An indicative screenshot indicating the information that have been extracted from a Polish hub about disability

As regards the format for storing the results of the extraction, we agreed that a set of comma-separated-values (CSV) or tabular data (XLS format) is sufficient. In total we produced one file in XLS format for each country. Each file contained one sheet for each hub/subhub that was given. Figure 3 shows an indicative screenshot from the results that have been extracted from Polish hub that described above.

#	Category	Title	URL	Description	Contact Info	e-mail	Date	ZIP
1				http://www.siepomaga.pl/k/niepełnosprawni/f				
3	1 Disability	Fundacja Blisko	http://fundacjabliskociebie.pl	Fundacja Blisko Ciebie została założona 13 Maja 13 41-200, Sosnowiec	Tel.: 32 298 77 77			41-200
4	2 Disability	Stowarzyszenie "Razem"	http://www.stowarzyszenierazem.org.pl	Stowarzyszenie "Razem" powstało z Piasta 35 44-200, Rybnik	Tel.: 530-770-425			44-200
5	3 Disability	Fundacja Q-Słońce	http://qsloncu.com.pl	Fundacja Q-Słońcu powstała w listopadzie Armii Ludowej 65 27-400, Ostrowiec Świętokrzyski	Tel.: 603416 27-400			27-400
6	4 Disability	Fundacja Beski	http://fundacja.beskidzkazima.pl	Fundacja Beskidzka Zima propaguje i Kłęczany 106 38-333, Kłęczany	Tel.: 669 505 922			38-333
7	5 Disability	Fundacja Światło	http://www.fundacjaswiatloko.pl	Pomagamy przede wszystkim podopiecznym Morska 1, lok. 2 81-764, Sopot	Tel.: 509 665 563			81-764
8	6 Disability	Ogólnopolskie	http://www.rettsyndrome.pl	Ogólnopolskie Stowarzyszenie Pomo ul. Białoprądnicka 24d/33 31-221, Kraków	Tel.: 604 151 484			31-221
9	7 Disability	Stowarzyszenie	http://www.przystannaszchodzieci.org	Działalność na rzecz aktywizacji dzieci Ks. Malinowskiego 05-410, Józefów	Tel.: 661950145			05-410
10	8 Disability	Fundacja	Gluch http://fgzaciszce.pl	Celem Fundacji Gluchych "Zaciszce" jest Odkryta 29E/44 03-140, Warszawa	Tel.: 888291031	biurofgz@gmail.com		03-140
11	9 Disability	Fundacja	Dzieci http://www.dzieciwujatoma.pl	Idea powołania Fundacji Dzieci Wujki Sosnowa 15 42-274, Aleksandria Druga	Tel.: 42-274			42-274
12	10 Disability	Fundacja	Dotyk http://www.fundacjadotykiepla.pl	Fundacja wspiera dzieci i ich rodziny, Ryzowa 48/116 02-495, Warszawa	Tel.: 533-722-998			02-495
13	11 Disability	FUNDACJA	FO http://www.fundacjaforani.org	Misja Fundacji Forani: Fundacja Fora MARSZAŁKOWSKA 7 00-626, Warszawa	Tel.: 508301144			00-626
14	12 Disability	Stowarzyszenie	http://www.dacszansze.pl	Stowarzyszenie Rodziców i Opiekunów os. XX - lecia 1 34-100, Wadowice	Tel.: 695727833			34-100
15	13 Disability	Fundacja	Dzieki http://www.dziekitobie.pl	O FUNDACJI Choroba dziecka to dla Solna 9/4 61-736, Poznań	Tel.: 570307309			61-736
16	14 Disability	Stowarzyszenie	http://www.sprawniejsi.pl	Stowarzyszenie Sprawniejsi.pl aktywizuje Nieznanowice 15 29-100, Włoszczowa	Tel.: 514 350 310			29-100
17	15 Disability	Polskie	Towarzystwo http://www.ptsr.org.pl	Pomagamy chorym na stwardnienie r Nowolipki 2A 00-160, Warszawa	Tel.: 22 241 3986			00-160
18	16 Disability	Europejska	Fun http://www.efos.org.pl	Europejska Fundacja Opieki Senioralnej Kazimierza Wielkiego 7/5 65-047, Zielona Góra	Tel.: 575-900-791, 65-047			65-047
19	17 Disability	Stowarzyszenie	http://www.ataksja.org.pl	W roku 2004 zostało powołane Stow. Edwarda Dembowskiego 16 / 59 02-784, Warszawa	Tel.: 60082617 02-784			02-784
20	18 Disability	Fundacja	na Rz http://www.arkadia.torun.pl	Swoje działania kierujemy przede ws: Młyska 2-4 87-100, Toruń	Tel.: (056) 654 84 81			87-100
21	19 Disability	Fundacja	Współ http://www.wspolnymkrokiem.pl	Jesteśmy młodą organizacją porażką Legnicka 65 54-206, Wrocław	Tel.: 600762302			54-206
22	20 Disability	Fundacja	Helpful http://www.fundacjahh.org	Fundacja Helpful Hand jest Organizac Kalwaryjska 32/11 30-504, Kraków	Tel.: 123415036			30-504
23	21 Disability	Fundacja	Urobos http://fundacjauroboros.pl	Fundacja Urobos, założona w roku: Bydgoska 1/31 26-600, Cały kraj	Tel.: 787240126			26-600
24	22 Disability	Fundacja	Król i http://www.krolismok.pl	Fundacja "Król i Smok" to fundacja Jutrzenki 4 55-080, Wrocław	Tel.: 502205929			55-080

Figure 3. A screenshot from the extracted information from a Polish hub about disability

2.2 Cleaning

After the extraction of the information from the hubs/subhubs and the individual websites, we started cleaning specific information. These activities were necessary for preparing them for

the next phase (merging phase). The activities were focused on cleaning and homogenizing the extracted URLs. More specifically we performed the following:

- Removed whitespace characters that either precede or follow the URL of an organization. This means that the URLs “ <http://transsol.eu>” and “<http://transsol.eu> ” were transformed to “<http://transsol.eu>”.
- Removed trailing ‘/’ character from the URLs of the organizations. This means that the URL “<http://transsol.eu/>” was transformed to “<http://transsol.eu>”.
- Checked if all the URLs were starting using either http:// or https://. This means that the URL “transsol.eu” was transformed “<http://transsol.eu>” and similarly the URL “www.google.com” was transformed to “<http://www.google.com>”.

The cleaning and homogenization of the URLs of the organizations was a crucial task, since without them, we would be unable to perform the activities of the merging phase. In particular we would be unable to check whether two URLs are equal or not.

2.3 Merging

The final step was the merging of the different lists that have been extracted. As already described above, for each country we created a single file in XLS format, containing multiple sheets; one for each hub. The sheets contained the extracted information for the three categories (disability, migration, unemployment), and some generic ones for some countries (i.e. humanitarian). The purpose of the merging process is to merge all the contents from the sheets of the same categories into a single sheet. This means that we should identify duplicate entries (i.e. information about the same organization) and merge them appropriately. Below describe in detail the steps that have been followed for the extracted lists of each country.

1. For each category (i.e. disability, migration, unemployment, etc.) we created a single sheet containing all the information of the corresponding category (without updating, or eliminating anything). This resulted in a file in XLS format with one sheet for each category.
2. For each category we searched for possible duplicate entries by searching over the URLs. For the identified duplicate entries we checked if they refer to the same organization, by checking other information such as the title, the description, the contact information, etc. If they refer to the same organization we merged them to one.
3. Since many of the identified organizations did not contain a URL, we searched for duplicate entries using their title and followed the same approach as in step 2.

We should note that in the steps 2 and 3 we did not merge organizations containing the same URL (or the same title) if the locations of the organizations were different (i.e. different addresses).

2.4 Sampling

The final steps is necessary for selecting the particular organizations from the lists produced after the merging process. The selected organization should have a transnational scope. This will be achieved by discovering the organizations that have a title, that indicates that their scope is transnational. The identification will be made using a list of keywords that are

provided. More specifically for each country two lists will be exploited; the first one containing a list of keywords (and their possible abbreviations) in English, and the second one containing the list of keywords (and their possible abbreviations) in the language of the corresponding country. The keywords are provided in the Appendix.

This process will produce one list (in the form of an excel file) for each country containing the organizations that were selected, indicating also the keyword that was found within their title (at least one keyword if more than one are found). Furthermore a list containing all the selected organizations for all countries will be produced. A summary of the results from the sampling process is given in Section 4.3.

3 The Tools

This section describes the tools we used for analyzing the networks. Some of these tools are publicly available tools, while others have been designed and developed for this purpose.

3.1 WebScrapper

WebScrapper is a JAVA application, developed by FORTH, for analyzing the contents of a website. WebScrapper takes as input the URL of the network, analyzes the contents of the network, and exports two files containing information about the identified sites: (a) a file (in XLS format) containing all the information about the identified sites and (b) a file (in TXT format) containing the URLs of the identified sites. The first file is intended for humans and for each identified site, it contains:

- A title
- The URL of the site
- Contact information (address, postal code, city)
- E-mail address
- A description
- The date it was created/updated

Of course these information are not always available (e.g. in many networks the date field is absent), therefore for each network we exported whatever is available. The second file is produced in order to be used from another application for downloading the contents of the sites.

3.2 Selenium

Selenium² offers a suite of tools for automating various functionalities with web browsers. Selenium offers the methods for enabling the test-automation for web-based applications. The entire suite of tools results in a rich set of testing functions specifically geared to the needs of testing of web applications of all types. These operations are highly flexible, allowing many options for locating UI elements and comparing expected test results against actual application behavior. One of Selenium's key features is the support for executing one's tests on multiple browser platforms.

² <http://www.seleniumhq.org/>

The Selenium suite has been particularly useful in the cases where information from a hub/sub hub was not organized properly and it required a lot of user interactions (i.e. various clicks on several links) to retrieve the actual content. Selenium allowed us to mimic the user behavior and retrieve the required information.

3.3 Custom JavaScript procedures

JavaScript is a programming language used to make web pages interactive. For the creation of an interactive web page, the developer mixes the actual content with JavaScript functions. In some cases it might be easier to extract the contents of a web site, by downloading the website and modifying the JavaScript code to show the contents in a particular form (i.e. as CSV values).

3.4 OpenRefine

OpenRefine³ is an open-source application for data cleanup and data transformation to several formats. These functionalities are performed over a set of rows of data which are separated into different columns. This schema resembles the relational database tables schema. The user can then define the set of operations that will be performed over the rows, including the transformation of the values of a cell based on its contents or the contents of another cell, the creation of a new value in a cell based on other values in other cells. The cleaned data set can then be exported in a variety of different formats including CSV, XML, RDF, JSON, etc.

³ <http://openrefine.org/>

4 The Results

This section provides a summary of the results from the analysis of the networks. At first we provide a summary of the results for the networks of all the eight countries, as they have been derived after the data clean up / data merging activities. Afterwards we will provide the detailed results for each country.

4.1 Summary of the results

The following table shows the results from the analysis of the networks of the eight countries. The table contains the number of entries that have been recognized, as well as the total number of entries with respect to the different categories. These results are the final ones after performing the three first processes that are described in Section 2 (Extraction, Cleaning, Merging).

Country	Disability	Migration	Unemployment	General/Humanitarian	Total
Denmark	260	267	150	243	920
France	2659	369	247	-	3275
Germany	5513	2242	8125	-	15880
Greece	1079	651	190	3426	5346
Italy	1385	2459	1027	-	4871
Poland	1844	288	376	-	2508
Switzerland	852	646	330	-	1828
UK	558	394	1086	-	2038
Total	14150	7316	11531	3669	36666

Table 1. A summary of the results for the eight countries

4.2 Detailed results

4.2.1 Denmark

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	5
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	6
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	6
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Humanitarian	1
Number of Individual websites about Disability	25
Number of Individual websites about Migration	16
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	21
Number of Individual websites about Humanitarian	153

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [Ds_1]. <http://www.handicap.dk/>
 [Ds_2]. <http://sjaeldnediagnoser.dk/medlemsforeninger/>
 [Ds_3]. <https://www.oliviadanmark.dk/links/>
 [Ds_4]. <http://www.startsiden.dk/Handicaphjaelp>
 [Ds_5]. <https://www.iapo.org.uk/search/node/denmark>, ...?page=1 - ... ?page=5

- [Mg_1]. <https://da.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kategori:Ngo%27er>
 [Mg_2]. <http://www.globaltfokus.dk/om-os/medlemmer>
 [Mg_3]. <http://refugeeswelcome.dk/en/link-list/>
 [Mg_4]. <http://www.bedsteforaeldreforasyl.dk/index.php?id=9>
 [Mg_5]. <http://www.enar-eu.org/denmark>
 [Mg_6]. <http://www.sosmodracisme.dk/?Links> Organisationer i Danmark

- [Un_1]. <http://frivilligjob.jobbank.dk/job/?act=find&opslag=0&opslag=1&key=arbejds%26oslash%3Bs&kseparat>
 or=or
 [Un_2]. <http://cv.dk/fagforeninger/>
 [Un_3]. <http://www.fagforening-portalen.dk/fagforenings-oversigt/>
 [Un_4]. <http://www.eapn.eu/en/who-we-are/who-we-are-members/danemu-danish-network-against-exclusion-eapn-denmark>
 [Un_5]. <http://www.epsu.org/r/47>
 [Un_6]. <http://www.feantsa.org/spip.php?article206&lang=en>

- [Hu_1]. <http://u-landsnyt.dk/organisationer>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	ZIP	Date	Misc.
[Ds_1]	33	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		
[Ds_2]	53	✓	✓						
[Ds_3]	16	✓	✓			✓			
[Ds_4]	100	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		Disability type
[Ds_5]	57	✓	✓			✓			
[Ds_Ind]	25	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_1]	101	✓	✓			✓		✓ (last update)	
[Mg_2]	78	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_3]	24	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	ZIP	Date	Misc.
[Mg_4]	30	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_5]	10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_6]	55	✓	✓						
[Mg_Ind]	16	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Un_1]	26	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓ (last update)	
[Un_2]	63	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Un_3]	69	✓	✓						
[Un_4]	14	✓	✓	✓			✓		
[Un_5]	15	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Un_6]	6	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		
[Un_Ind]	21	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Hu_1]	196	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Hu_Ind]	153	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

4.2.2 France

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	12
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment - Precarious	11
Number of Individual websites about Migration	11

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

[Ds_1]. <http://www.santemagazine.fr/annuaire-associations-patients>

[Ds_2]. <http://www.unacs.org/category/Associations>

[Mg_1]. <http://cfda.rezo.net>

[Mg_2]. <http://www.raidh.org/Associations-et-ONG-de-defense-de.html>

[Mg_3]. http://www.lacimade.org/la_cimade/cimade/rubriques/112-r-seaux-

[Mg_4]. <http://www.gisti.org/spip.php?article6>

[Mg_5]. <http://www.fasti.org/index.php/les-asti27>

[Mg_6]. <http://www.amnesty.fr/>

[Mg_7]. <http://www.ldh-france.org/>

[Mg_8]. http://www.inegalites.fr/spip.php?page=comprendre_analyses&id_mot=25&id_rubrique=110

[Mg_9]. <http://www.migdev.org/qui-sommes-nous/partenaires/>

[Mg_10]. <http://www.france-terre-asile.org/les-etablissements/centres-france-terre-d-asile/centre-france-terre-d-asile>

[Mg_11]. <http://gas.asso.pagesperso-orange.fr/liens.html>

[Mg_12]. http://www.tousbenevoles.org/trouver-une-mission-benevole?cp=&id_action_type=13&id_public=8&q=&age_minimum=0

[Un_1]. <http://www.ripess.eu/governance/members-network/>

[Un_2]. https://www.dmoz.org/World/Fran%C3%A7ais/Soci%C3%A9t%C3%A9/Associations_et_organisations/P/Protection_du_travail/

[Un_3]. <http://www.mncp.fr/site/federation/nos-partenaires/les-mouvements-chomeurs-organisations-proches/>

[Un_4]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Associations-de-Defense-des-Chomeurs-et-autres/index.php>

[Un_5]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Alternatifs-independants-et-autres/index.php>

[Un_6]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Emploi-sites-specialises/index.php>

[Un_7]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Economique-Social/index.php>

[Un_8]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Creation-Orientation-Formation/index.php>

[Un_9]. <http://www.actuchomage.org/Notre-selection-de-liens/Juridique-Administratif/index.php>

[Un_10]. http://cicade.asso.free.fr/page_4.php

[Un_11]. <http://equipement.paris.fr/point-d-acces-au-droit-p-a-d-19e-1216#local-calendar>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	ZIP	Date	Misc.
[Ds_1]	2663	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		Territory, Disease
[Ds_2]	6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (last update)	
[Mg_1]	40	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_2]	10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_3]	27	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_4]	32	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		Type
[Mg_5]	58	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (active since)	
[Mg_6]	1	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[Mg_7]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_8]	1	✓	✓	✓			✓		
[Mg_9]	90	✓	✓						Type
[Mg_10]	56	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (creation date)	
[Mg_11]	30	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_12]	55	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[Mg_Ind]	11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Un_1]	29	✓	✓			✓			Activity type
[Un_2]	24	✓	✓			✓			Province
[Un_3]	24	✓	✓						
[Un_4]	44	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_5]	42	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_6]	6	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_7]	30	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_8]	19	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_9]	11	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_10]	24	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[Un_11]	5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

4.2.3 Germany

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	24
Number of Individual websites about Disability	1170
Number of Individual websites about Migration	1867
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	258

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [Ds_1]. <http://www.netzwerkinklusion.de/inklusionslandkarte>
- [Ds_2]. <http://www.lebenshilfe.de/de/organisationensuche/index.php?plz=&ort=&bundesland=&organisationsart=21100LHI#einrichtungenMap>
- [Mg_1]. <https://www.google.com/maps/d/viewer?mid=zc6TdvfelKuY.kUvriXoSREXw>
- [Mg_2]. <https://www.google.com/maps/d/viewer?mid=zihaJpb9Xb1o.kmlSmlSzU7kw>
- [Un_1]. <https://www.menschistmensch.de/helfer-liste/>
- [Un_2]. http://www.paritaet-bw.de/no_cache/verband/mitglieder/unsere-mitglieder/nach-namen.html
- [Un_3]. http://www.paritaet-bw.de/no_cache/verband/mitglieder/unsere-mitglieder/nach-fachberatung.html
- [Un_4]. <http://www.paritaet-bayern.de/der-verband/bezirksverbaende/>
- [Un_5]. http://mittelfranken.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_6]. http://oberfranken.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_7]. http://unterfranken.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_8]. http://niederbayern-oberpfalz.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_9]. http://oberbayern.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_10]. http://schwaben.paritaet-bayern.de/mitgliedsorganisationen/mitgliedsorganisationen-nach-alphabet/?no_cache=1
- [Un_11]. <https://www.paritaet-berlin.de/nc/mitglieder/mitglieder-nach-arbeitsschwerpunkten.html>
- [Un_12]. <http://www.paritaet-brb.de/content/e5561/e9412/>
- [Un_13]. <http://www.paritaet-bremen.de/mitgliedsorganisationen.html>
- [Un_14]. <http://www.paritaet-hamburg.de/verband/mitgliedschaft/unsere-mitglieder.html> - http://www.paritaet-hamburg.de/fileadmin/Verband/MO-Liste_fuer_Internet_11_2015.pdf
- [Un_15]. <http://www.paritaet-hessen.org/ueber-uns/unsere-mitglieder.html>
- [Un_16]. <http://paritaet-mv.de/ueber-uns/unsere-mitglieder.html>
- [Un_17]. http://www.paritaetischer.de/landesverband/top/mitglieder/nach_fachbereich.html?time=1449839485169
- [Un_18]. http://www.paritaet-nrw.org/content/ueber_uns/mitglieder/ueberregional/index_ger.html
- [Un_19]. http://www.paritaet-nrw.org/content/ueber_uns/mitglieder/oertlich/index_ger.html
- [Un_20]. <http://www.paritaet-rheinland-pfalz-saarland.de/index.php?id=20>
- [Un_21]. http://parisax.de/www/cms/front_content.php?idcat=21 - ... 26
- [Un_22]. http://www.paritaet-lsa.de/cms/index.php?article_id=40&buchstabe=A - ... Z
- [Un_23]. <http://www.paritaet-sh.de/de/ueberuns/mitglieder/start.htm>
- [Un_24]. <https://www.paritaet-th.de/mo-liste/>
- [Gn_1]. <http://www.ngo.at/europa/netzwerke-in-europa>
- [Gn_2]. <http://www.welcomeurope.com/european-networks-database.html>
- [Gn_3]. <http://www.ngo-platform-asylum-migration.eu/>
- [Gn_4]. <http://www.ngovoice.org/>

[Gn_5]. <http://www.hrdn.eu/about-us/members/>

[Gn_6]. <http://ifp-fip.org/en>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	565	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (registered)	✓	
[Ds_2]	5923	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_Ind]	1170	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_1]	708	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_2]	198	✓	✓						
[Mg_Ind]	1867	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[Un_1]	304	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_2]	845	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_3]	27	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_4]	6	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_5]	131	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_6]	54	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_7]	49	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_8]	61	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_9]	416	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_10]	407	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_11]	53	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_12]	317	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_13]	23	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_14]	360	✓							
[Un_15]	811	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_16]	198	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_17]	70	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_18]	87	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_19]	2783	✓	✓	✓				✓	Territory
[Un_20]	684	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_21]	477	✓	✓						
[Un_22]	290	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_23]	47	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	
[Un_24]	332	✓	✓	✓				✓	
[Un_Ind]	258	✓	✓	✓		✓			
[Gn_1]	21	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[Gn_2]	51	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[Gn_3]	29	✓	✓		✓	✓			
[Gn_4]	80	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[Gn_5]	48	✓	✓		✓	✓			
[Gn_6]	63	✓	✓		✓	✓			

4.2.4 Greece

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	4
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about General issues	2
Number of Individual websites about Disability	698
Number of Individual websites about Migration	197
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	91

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

[Ds_1]. <http://www.moh.gov.gr/articles/citizen/c69-xrhimoi-syndesmoi/352-syllogoi-asthenwn>

[Ds_2]. <http://www.esaea.gr/about-us/members>

[Mg_1]. <http://culturalsynergie.blogspot.gr/p/blog-page.html>

[Mg_2]. <http://www.migrants.gr/?cat=29>

[Un_1]. <https://bookworker.wordpress.com/%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BD%CE%B4%CE%B5%CF%83%CE%BC%CE%BF%CE%B9/>

[Un_2]. <http://anergoigeitonion.espivblogs.net/%CE%B5%CE%BD%CE%B4%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%86%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%BF%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B5%CF%82-%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CF%8C%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%80%CE%BF%CE%B9/>

[Un_3]. <https://anticalcenter.wordpress.com/>

[Un_4]. <http://katalipsiesiea.blogspot.gr/>

[Gn_1]. www.enallaktikos.gr

[Gn_2]. <http://www.solidarity4all.gr/>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	98	✓	✓						Domain
[Ds_2]	477	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Type
[Ds_Ind]	698	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Type
[Mg_1]	118	✓	✓						Type
[Mg_2]	393	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	Type
[Mg_Ind]	197	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_1]	29	✓	✓						
[Un_2]	23	✓	✓						
[Un_3]	27	✓	✓						
[Un_4]	88	✓	✓						
[Un_Ind]	91	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Type
[Gn_1]	3372	✓	✓	✓				✓	
[Gn_2]	380	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

4.2.5 Italy

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	26
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	28
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	19
Number of Individual websites about Disability	42
Number of Individual websites about Migration	69
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	44

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [Ds_1]. <http://www.disabilitaliani.org/Link.htm>
- [Ds_2]. <http://www.fishonlus.it/fish-onlus/aderenti/>
- [Ds_3]. <http://www.ridsnetwork.org/en/who-we-are/>
- [Ds_4]. <http://www.ledha.it/page.asp?menu1=3&menu2=10>
- [Ds_5]. http://www.superabile.it/web/it/SUPERABILE_MULTIMEDIA/Siti_Utili/index.html
- [Ds_6]. http://www.aice-epilessia.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=22&Itemid=55
- [Ds_7]. <http://aipd.it/>
- [Ds_8]. <http://www.aism.it/strutture.aspx>
- [Ds_9]. <http://www.anglat.it/index.php?pg=42&id=149#.Vrh-W9DQMOY>
- [Ds_10]. http://www.anmic.it/Sedi_regionali.aspx
- [Ds_11]. <http://www.anmil.it/Sedi/tabid/475/language/en-US/Default.aspx>
- [Ds_12]. <http://www.apici.org/about/dove-siamo2>
- [Ds_13]. <http://www.arpaonlus.org/>
- [Ds_14]. http://www.spinabifidaitalia.it/it/cs_le_associazioni_sul_territorio.php
- [Ds_15]. <http://www.dpitalia.org/link-utili/>
- [Ds_16]. <http://www.ens.it/sedi-periferiche-ens>
- [Ds_17]. <http://www.fiadda.it/links/>
- [Ds_18]. <https://www.uiciechi.it/organizzazione/regioni/indiceregioni.asp>
- [Ds_19]. <http://www.uidm.org/dove-siamo/>
- [Ds_20]. http://unms.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=53&Itemid=70
- [Ds_21]. http://www.consorziomeridia.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=54&Itemid=58
- [Ds_22]. <http://www.diaconiavaldese.org/linea4/dovesiamo.php>
- [Ds_23]. <http://www.istitutoferretti.it/>
- [Ds_24]. <http://www.diaconiavaldese.org/linea2/vittoria.php>
- [Ds_25]. <http://www.diaconiavaldese.org/gignoro/index.php>
- [Ds_26]. <http://www.ensmilano.it/link/>
- [Mg_1]. <http://centroastalli.it/category/rete-territoriale/>
- [Mg_2]. <http://www.ong.it/chi-siamo/i-soci/>
- [Mg_3]. <http://www.sosrazzismo.it/joomla/invia-un-web-link/link.html>
- [Mg_4]. <http://www.concorditalia.org/chi-siamo/membri/>
- [Mg_5]. <http://www.cocis.it/ong-associate.html?limitstart=0>
- [Mg_6]. <http://www.yallaitalia.it/>
- [Mg_7]. <http://www.litaliasonoanchio.it/>
- [Mg_8]. <http://www.secondegenerazioni.it/>
- [Mg_9]. <http://www.municipio.re.it/retecivica/urp/pes.nsf/web/ntwrk>
- [Mg_10]. <http://www.cronachediordinariorazzismo.org/>
- [Mg_11]. <http://fortresseurope.blogspot.it/>
- [Mg_12]. <http://giovanimusulmani.it/>
- [Mg_13]. <http://www.stranieriitalia.it/>
- [Mg_14]. <http://www.giornalismi.info/mediarom/>
- [Mg_15]. <http://www.associna.com/it/>
- [Mg_16]. <http://www.santegidio.org/>
- [Mg_17]. <http://primomarzo2010.blogspot.it/>
- [Mg_18]. <http://www.lvvia.it/>

- [Mg_19]. <http://www.cies.it/>
[Mg_20]. <http://www.cnca.it/>
[Mg_21]. <http://www.emmaus.it/>
[Mg_22]. <http://www.acli.it/>
[Mg_23]. <http://www.culturaalbanese.it/index.php?lang=it>
[Mg_24]. <http://terradelfuoco.org/>
[Mg_25]. <http://www.perlapace.it/>
[Mg_26]. http://www.caritasitaliana.it/home_page/sul_territorio/00003499_Sul_Territorio.html
[Mg_27]. <http://arci.it/sedi>
[Mg_28]. <http://www.diaconiavaldese.org/linea2/migranti.php>
- [Un_1]. <http://assolavoro.eu/aziende-associate>
[Un_2]. <http://www.cris.it/index.php>
[Un_3]. <http://www.cgm.coop/index.php/en/network/consortia>
[Un_4]. <http://www.retelavoro.org/index.html>
[Un_5]. <http://www.cgil.it/Sedi/Default.aspx> - <http://www.cgil.it/Links/Default.aspx>
[Un_6]. <http://www.cisl.it/la-cisl/federazioni-di-categoria.html> - <http://www.cisl.it/la-cisl/enti-associazioni-e-centri-di-attivita.html>
[Un_7]. <http://www.uil.it/uilservizi/>
[Un_8]. <http://www.cobas.it/Link-Cobas> - <http://pubblicoimpiego.cobas.it/pubblicoimpiego/COBAS-LINK/Siti-Cobas>
[Un_9]. <http://www.ugl.it/siti-ugl/>
[Un_10]. <http://www.assosomm.it/associati/>
[Un_11]. <http://www.legacoop.coop/associazione/legacoop-territoriali/>
[Un_12]. <http://www.confcooperative.it/LAssociazione/Noi-sul-territorio>
[Un_13]. <http://www.agci.it/content/territorio>
[Un_14]. <http://www.cilap.eu/index.php/collegamenti-web>
[Un_15]. <http://www.evtnetwork.it/en/about-us/partners.html>
[Un_16]. <http://www.csabelelavoro.it/presentazione/le-consorziate/>
[Un_17]. <http://www.retedellaconoscenza.it>
[Un_18]. <http://www.act-agire.it/>
[Un_19]. <http://www.cauto.it/la-rete/>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	17	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_2]	42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_3]	4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_4]	26	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Region, Issue
[Ds_5]	112	✓	✓						
[Ds_6]	46	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_7]	51	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_8]	399	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_9]	41	✓	✓						
[Ds_10]	18	✓		✓				✓	
[Ds_11]	102	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_12]	27	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_13]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_14]	16	✓	✓	✓	✓				
[Ds_15]	11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_16]	123	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_17]	21	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_18]	125	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_19]	66	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_20]	105	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_21]	14	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (creation date)	✓	
[Ds_22]	24	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_23]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_24]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_25]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_26]	29	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_Ind]	42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_1]	7	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_2]	87	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_3]	20	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_4]	49	✓							
[Mg_5]	20	✓	✓	✓				✓	Region
[Mg_6]	109	✓	✓	✓	✓				
[Mg_7]	2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_8]	1	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_9]	31	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_10]	15	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_11]	1	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		
[Mg_12]	42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_13]	19	✓	✓						
[Mg_14]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓				
[Mg_15]	12	✓	✓						
[Mg_16]	8	✓	✓						
[Mg_17]	2	✓	✓						
[Mg_18]	30	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_19]	3	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_20]	256	✓		✓	✓			✓	Region, District
[Mg_21]	18	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_22]	155	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_23]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_24]	2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_25]	2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_26]	217	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Mg_27]	1358	✓	✓	✓	✓				
[Mg_28]	4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_Ind]	69	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_1]	54	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_2]	5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_3]	68	✓	✓	✓				✓	
[Un_4]	10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Un_5]	96	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Region
[Un_6]	31	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_7]	337	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_8]	20	✓	✓						
[Un_9]	38	✓	✓						Type
[Un_10]	27	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_11]	89	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Territory
[Un_12]	104	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_13]	54	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Territory, Type
[Un_14]	19	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_15]	5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_16]	5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (active since)	✓	
[Un_17]	17	✓	✓						
[Un_18]	9	✓	✓						
[Un_19]	4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_Ind]	44	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

4.2.6 Poland

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	14
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	2
Number of Individual websites about Disability	13
Number of Individual websites about Migration	31
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	7

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [Ds_1]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=65&baza=3
 [Ds_2]. <http://www.siepomaga.pl/k/niepenosprawni/f>

- [Mg_1]. http://www.migrant.info.pl/Organizacje_i_instytucje_pomagaj%C4%85ce_migrantom.html
 [Mg_2]. <http://www.uchodzca.org.pl/instytucje.html>
 [Mg_3]. <http://www.forummigracyjne.org.pl/aktualnosci.php?news=356&wid=32>
 [Mg_4]. <http://zagranica.org.pl/uchodzcy-w-polsce-i-na-swiecie/organizacje-czlonkowskie-grupy-zagranica-zaangazowane-w-tematyke>
 [Mg_5]. <http://study-in-wroclaw.pl/studiuji-w-wroclawiu/poradnik-studenta/organizacje-wspierajace-cudzoziemcow/>
 [Mg_6]. http://www.naszwybor.org.pl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=48&Itemid=56
 [Mg_7]. <http://mam-prawo.org/opcje/jestem-cudzoziemcem-w-polsce/przydatne-kontakty/organizacje-pomagajace-cudzoziemcom/>
 [Mg_8]. http://www.malopolska.uw.gov.pl/default.aspx?page=organizacje_na_rzecz_cudzoziemcow
 [Mg_9]. <http://www.mpips.gov.pl/userfiles/File/mps/pomocowe.pdf>
 [Mg_10]. http://www.mpips.gov.pl/userfiles/File/Departament%20Pomocy%20Spolesznej/cudzoziemcy%20uchodzy/organizacje_na_rzecz_cudzoziemcow_maj_2009.pdf
 [Mg_11]. <http://www.iom.pl/>
 [Mg_12]. <http://www.interwencjaprawna.pl/glowna.html>
 [Mg_13]. <http://www.ecre.org/>
 [Mg_14]. <http://www.unhcr-centraleurope.org/pl/index.html>

- [Un_1]. <http://siecpirp.rynekpracy.org/wyszukiwarka>
 [Un_2]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_woj=1&kryt_forma=&kryt_klient=&kryt_typ=&szukanie=bezrob

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	1551	✓	✓	✓			✓ (active since)	✓	
[Ds_2]	297	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	
[Ds_Ind]	13	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_1]	155	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Type
[Mg_2]	33	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_3]	24	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_4]	13	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_5]	15	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_6]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (created)	✓	
[Mg_7]	34	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_8]	2	✓	✓			✓			

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Mg_9]	24	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_10]	26	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_11]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_12]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_13]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[Mg_14]	1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_Ind]	31	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_1]	123	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_2]	251	✓	✓	✓			✓ (active since)	✓	
[Un_Ind]	7	✓	✓						

4.2.7 Switzerland

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	6
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	14
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	10
Number of Individual websites about Disability	88
Number of Individual websites about Migration	107
Number of Individual websites about Unemployment	68

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [Ds_1]. <http://www.insieme-ge.ch/pratique/adresses-utiles/>
- [Ds_2]. <http://www.fondation-ensemble.ch/divers/liens-utiles/>
- [Ds_3]. <http://www.agis-ge.ch/liens-web>
- [Ds_4]. <https://www.ge.ch/handicap/repertoire/repertoire.asp>
- [Ds_5]. <http://www.curaviva.ch/Associazione/Partner-e-Link/Paqah/>
- [Ds_6]. <http://www.forum-handicap-ne.ch/liens/>
-
- [Mg_1]. <http://www.pluriels.ch/documentation/liens-utiles>
- [Mg_2]. <http://www.stopexclusion.ch/organisations-membres/>
- [Mg_3]. <http://www.sosf.ch/de/service/linksammlung/index.html>
- [Mg_4]. <http://droit-de-rester.blogspot.ch/p/une-liste-de-liens-utiles-collectifs.html>
- [Mg_5]. <http://movimentodeisenzavoce.org/link/>
- [Mg_6]. <http://www.swiss-solidarity.org/en.html>
- [Mg_7]. <http://www.humanrights.ch/fr/>
- [Mg_8]. <http://www.kultura.ch/>
- [Mg_9]. <http://www.mentoratemploimigration.ch/>
- [Mg_10]. <http://www.esprit-nomade.ch/>
- [Mg_11]. <https://www.heks.ch/>
- [Mg_12]. <http://www.sah-schweiz.ch/>
- [Mg_13]. <http://www.terre-des-femmes.ch/de>
- [Mg_14]. <http://www.gefluechtet.ch/>
-
- [Un_1]. <http://adc-ge.ch/liens/38-associations-actives-dans-notre-reseau-suisse->
- [Un_2]. <http://adc-ge.ch/liens/39-autres-associations-a-geneve->
- [Un_3]. <http://www.capas-ge.ch/new/membres>
- [Un_4]. <http://www.apres-ge.ch/>
- [Un_5]. <http://www.partage.ch/>
- [Un_6]. <http://www.t-interactions.ch/>
- [Un_7]. <http://oseo-vd.ch/>
- [Un_8]. <http://www.bateaugeneve.ch/>
- [Un_9]. <http://www.ville-geneve.ch/themes/social/partenaires-vie-associative/>
- [Un_10]. <http://www.trajets.org/>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	44	✓	✓			✓		✓	Type
[Ds_2]	50	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_3]	31	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_4]	273	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Ds_5]	65	✓	✓			✓			Domain
[Ds_6]	436	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Region, Type
[Ds_Ind]	88	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_1]	36	✓	✓	✓		✓			
[Mg_2]	42	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_3]	80	✓	✓			✓			
[Mg_4]	40	✓	✓	✓		✓			Province
[Mg_5]	21	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Region
[Mg_6]	25	✓	✓						
[Mg_7]	206	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_8]	60	✓	✓						Country
[Mg_9]	29	✓	✓						
[Mg_10]	15	✓							
[Mg_11]	56	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_12]	10	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_13]	20	✓	✓						
[Mg_14]	6	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Mg_Ind]	107	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_1]	8	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_2]	9	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_3]	34	✓	✓			✓			
[Un_4]	57	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_5]	53	✓	✓						
[Un_6]	8	✓		✓	✓			✓	
[Un_7]	28	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_8]	18	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_9]	118	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Domain
[Un_10]	22	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
[Un_Ind]	68	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

4.2.8 United Kingdom

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Disability	2
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Migration	4
Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs about Unemployment	3
Number of Individual websites about Migration	109

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

[Ds_1]. <http://www.disabilityrightsuk.org/membership/our-current-members>

[Ds_2]. <http://www.vodg.org.uk/members/list-of-vodg-members.html>

[Ds_3]. http://shop.mind.org.uk/help/mind_in_your_area?&shop=0&list=1

[Mg_1]. http://www.refugeecouncil.org.uk/about_refugee_council/members

[Mg_2]. <http://www.aviddetention.org.uk/visiting/visitors-groups>

[Mg_3]. <http://www.asaproject.org/research-publications/organisations-can-help/>

[Mg_4]. <http://noborders.org.uk/>

[Mg_5]. <http://www.star-network.org.uk/>

[Mg_6]. <https://cityofsanctuary.org/about/groups/groups/>

[Un_1]. <https://www.tuc.org.uk/britains-unions>

[Un_2]. <http://www.socialenterprise.org.uk/membership/our-members/members-directory>

[Un_3]. <http://www.socialenterprisescotland.org.uk/our-story/directory/>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	E-Mail	Description	Date	ZIP	Misc.
[Ds_1]	320	✓	✓						
[Ds_2]	81	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_3]	170	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Ds_Ind]	2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_1]	89	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_2]	17	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_3]	97	✓	✓	✓	✓				City
[Mg_4]	14	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	City
[Mg_5]	34	✓	✓						
[Mg_6]	79	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Mg_Ind]	116	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[Un_1]	51	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	Sector
[Un_2]	896	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	
[Un_3]	150	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (active since)	✓	Location, Sector

4.3 Summary of the results (transnational organizations)

The following table shows the results after performing the sampling process to select those organizations with a transnational scope. The process is described in detail in Section 2.4. The list of keywords for each country are given in the Appendix.

Country	Disability	Migration	Unemployment	General/Humanitarian	Total
Denmark	44	40	31	88	203
France	32	45	8	-	85
Germany	148	150	296	-	594
Greece	9	22	1	68	100
Italy	9	95	18	-	122
Poland	20	43	17	-	80
Switzerland	20	76	11	1	108
UK	11	50	52	-	113
Transnational	183	52	43	393	671
Total	476	573	477	550	2076

Table 2. A summary of the results as regards the transnational organizations

5 Conclusions

The main purpose of this deliverable was to describe the process for the analysis of the wide range of networks, organizations and groups engaged with innovative forms of transnational solidarity in times of crisis, such as citizens' initiatives and networks of cooperation amongst civil society actors, with a strong focus on the fields of unemployment, migration, disabilities.

The process included 2 main activities: (a) extracting particular information about such organizations and groups as they can be found from a set of representative hubs, and storing them in a form suitable for further analysis (in an Excel File) and (b) merging the produced lists into a single one, and omitting any duplicate occurrences of an organization.

The outcome that will be distributed to the TransSQL consortium is: (a) one Excel file for each country, containing the (merged) list of organizations that were found for each country, (b) one Excel file for each country, containing the organizations that were found for each hub; the results of each hub will be stored as a separate sheet in the file, and (c) the present deliverable that describes the entire process.

Appendix

International keywords (+ United Kingdom)

abroad, Africa, border, borders, British, Cosmop, cosmopol, cosmopolitan, cross-border, cross-cultural, Danish, diversity, Eur, Europ, Europa, Europe, European, Exil, Exiles, foreign, foreigners, Forein, German-Russian Integration Office, Glob, Global, globe, HELLAS, Integration, Inter, intercult, intercultural, intergrat, internat, international, Italy-China, melting pot, multicult, multicultural, people, peoples, supranational, Transborder, Transboundary, transnat, transnational, world, worldwide

Keywords for Denmark

afrika, dansk, europ, Europa, Europæisk, global, græns, grænse, integr, Integration, interkult, interkulturel, internat, International, kosmopol, kosmopolitisk, mangfoldighed, multikult, multikulturelle, smeltedigel, transnat, Transnational, tværkultur, tværkulturel, udland, udlandet, verden, verdensplan

Keywords for France

cosmopol, cosmopolite, creuset, étra, étrangers, europ, européen, exil, exiles, frontière, glob, global, intercultu, intercultural, internat, international, mond, monde, multicult, multicultural, peupl, peoples, transnat, transnational

Keywords for Germany

Afrika, Ausland, auslând, ausländisch, Auslands, Deutsch-Russisches Integrationswerk: Deutsch, Europ, Europa, europäisch, global, grenz, Grenze, grenzüberschreitend, interkult, interkulturell, internat, international, multikult, multikulturell, transnat, transnational, Völkerverständigung, Welt, weltoffen

Keywords for Greece

Διαπολιτισμική, Διαπολιτισμική, Διαπολιτισμικό, Διαπολιτισμικό, Διαπολιτισμικός, Διαπολιτισμικός, Διασυνοριακή, Διασυνοριακή, Διασυνοριακό, Διασυνοριακό, Διασυνοριακός, Διασυνοριακός, Διεθνείς, Διεθνείς, Διεθνες, Διεθνές, Διεθνη, Διεθνή, Διεθνης, Διεθνή, Διεθνους, Διεθνούς, Ευρωπαϊκά, Ευρωπαϊκά, Ευρωπαϊκή, Ευρωπαϊκή, Ευρωπαϊκό, Ευρωπαϊκό, Ευρωπαϊκού, Ευρωπαϊκού, Ευρώπη, Ευρωπη, Κοσμος, Κόσμος, Κοσμου, Κόσμου, Ξενοι, Ξένοι, Ξενος, Ξένος, Παγκοσμια, Παγκόσμια, Παγκοσμιος, Παγκόσμιος, Πανευρωπαϊκή, Πανευρωπαϊκή, Πανευρωπαϊκό, Πανευρωπαϊκό, Πανευρωπαϊκός, Πανευρωπαϊκός, Πολυπολιτισμική, Πολυπολιτισμική, Πολυπολιτισμικό, Πολυπολιτισμικό, Πολυπολιτισμικός, Συνορα, Σύνορα

Keywords for Italy

Africa, confin, confine, europ, Europa, europea, europeo, frontier, frontier, global, globale, intercultu, interculturale, internaz, internazionale, Italia-Cina, melting pot, mond, mondiale, multicult, multiculturale, popol, popoli, stranier, stranieri, transnaz, transnazionale

Keywords for Poland

europ, Europa, Europejska, Europejski, europejskie, Global, globalna, globalne, globalny, granic, granica, granice, kosmpolityczna, Kosmpolityczny, kosmpopolit, międzyn, miedzynarodowa, miedzynarodowe, Miedzynarodowe porozumienie, Międzynarodowy, Ogólnoświatowe, ponadna, ponadnarodowa, ponadnarodowe, Ponadnarodowy, ponadpaństwowa, ponadpaństwowe, Ponadpaństwowy, środkowoeuropejskie, Świat, światowa, światowe, światowy, transgraniczna, transgraniczne, Transgraniczny, Zagraniczne

Keywords for Switzerland

Africa, Afrika, Ausland, auslând, ausländisch, Auslands, confin, confine, cosmopol, cosmopolite, creuset, Deutsch-Russisches Integrationswerk: Deutsch, étra, étrangers, europ, Europa, europäisch, europea, européen, europeo, exil, exiles, frontier, frontier, frontière, glob, global, globale, grenz, Grenze, grenzüberschreitend, intercultu, interculturelle, intercultural, interkult, interkulturell, internat, international, internaz, internazionale, Italia-Cina, melting pot, mond, monde, mondiale, multicult, multiculturale, multicultural, multikult, multikulturell, peupl, peoples, popol, popoli, stranier, stranieri, transnat, transnational, transnaz, transnazionale, Völkerverständigung, Welt, weltoffen